

USE OF INFORMATICS TECHNOLOGY AND ETHICAL DILEMMA AMONG NURSES IN NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

Nurses face ethical dilemmas on a daily basis, no matter where they practice. An ethical dilemma or ethical paradox is a decision-making problem between two possible moral imperatives, neither of which is unambiguously acceptable or preferable. The complexity arises out of the situational conflict in which obeying one would result in transgressing another. These ethical dilemmas may be invoked to refute an ethical system or moral code, or to improve it so as to resolve the paradox. The use of information technology in nursing commonly known as nursing informatics sometimes interferes with nursing ethics in nursing care process, nursing research and even nursing education. The universal impact of technology in health care has created a call for nurses to improve their competences in information technology. There are many ethical issues nurses can face in the workplace which a proper understanding of informatics will streamline. Thus, developments in information systems with its social and political implications will require efficient ethical considerations in nursing care processes and procedures in Nigeria. Nursing leadership such as the Nursing and Midwifery Council of Nigeria (NMCN) and nursing education institutions will need to improve on their role to ensure enhance competence in informatics to effectively reduce the dilemma nurses go through using information technology in their workplace.

Keywords: *Ethical dilemma, Information technology, Nursing.*

INTRODUCTION

The Nursing and Midwifery Council of Nigeria (NMCN) has developed a Code of Ethics for Nurses, which has become a guide for the effective discharge of nursing responsibilities in a manner consistent with quality in nursing care and ethical responsibilities of the profession. These ethics are however influenced by many factors such as culture, religion, education, individual values and opinions and most recently information technology with the advent of smart phones.. These factors constantly interfere with ethical views and influence the

ethical decisions that affect nurses and their patients.

The core nursing values of protecting life and alleviating suffering are basically common among members of the medical and nursing profession. These codes; confidentiality, honesty and fellowship are also common within these groups. However, Jennifer Wilson (1986) pointed out that many nurses have different in the way they face dilemmas and context in which nurses and doctors consider professional ethics.

The advent of Information Technology has presented nurses all over the world with a clear and present dilemma on how to balance between Nursing ethics, moral and appropriate use of informatics in the discharge of Nursing care and Procedures. This open a perpetual paradox as social medial has completely made the world a global society.

The most common moral health is moral conflict in deciding how to balance the needs of "many" and "individual" rights such that individual privacy and freedom can be respected while still protecting and promoting the health of others. Greg Staplon et al (2014).

As observed by Margaret Lynch (2015), computer technologies for collecting, storing, manipulating and transmitting data has transformed how we use and distribute information. They also create moral dilemmas as the speed and efficiency of electronic information systems, such as local and global networks, databases and information processing programs. This has compelled people to face entirely new rights and responsibilities in their use of information and to review the standards of conduct formed prior to the advent of computers.

These circumstances require an appropriate level of moral decision-making such that defining a suitable path to take when facing difficult ethical dilemma can be very challenging. A group of specialized nurses should

thus be educated and prepared to take advantage of advancements in technology to enhance nursing care.

Today, the nursing profession is turning towards using computers for many areas of their daily tasks like documentation, communication between shifts, departments and even facilities and building an information database, the steps of utilizing information, applying knowledge to a problem and acting with wisdom form the basis of nursing practice. The use of computer technology to improve hospital operations and administration has been widely recognized. Specifically as a support tool for nurses, many researchers have found that while far from perfect, the technology is viewed positively if implemented more carefully.

The ever increasing burden of disease, in a resources constrained environment like Nigeria has made ethical issues for nurses very complex. Though nurse ethics are key to the quality of nursing care, not much has been documented about nurses' knowledge of ethics, formal training and ethics in service in developing countries like Nigeria.

Nurses are vital members of the health care system. They are constantly faced with crucial ethical issues in practice, as such Nurses are required to make difficult moral decisions rationally. Much has been written about the moral distress that nurses experience in

practice. The moral distress is attributed, at least in part, to the divided loyalties that nurses and SW feel in their work. They are often caught between what they believe may be better for their patients and institutional constraints or override the decisions of other healthcare professionals.

Little is known about how SW and nurses feel confident in their ability to deal with ethical issues and take appropriate ethical action.

In the line of duty, nurses often experiences moral distress arising from divided loyalty they face as they are in many cases caught between what they believe and know to be better for their patients and institutional constraints or overriding decision of other healthcare practitioners.

This results in great dilemma and interferes with their ability to deal with ethical issues and take appropriate ethical actions confidently.

Informatics ethics

The use of informatics in the field of healthcare has grown very rapidly. It has changed methods and methodologies in the field efficiently. The acceptance of information technologies, as well as enhancements in disease surveillance systems, large health database analysis tools and techniques, and increased access to health information through the implementation of electronic medical record systems, are all a powerful incentive for future advances in public healthcare.

Ken (2014) outlined the four basic ethics of informatics as presented by in 1997 by severson as;

(1) respect for information, (2) respect for privacy; (3) equitable representation; and (4) Non-maleficence.

Therefore, though informatics has become a prominent tool in nursing care and procedure issues surrounding privacy, confidentiality and integrity of information has become of great concern which portends a great dilemma between ethics and informatics in Nursing Practice. Thus human et al reported that despite the existence of existing literature on ethical issues in medicine, as well as ethics in computing, information technology in medicine lead to new ethical issues not covered by medical ethics or computing.

Nursing informatics has evolved into a mandatory focus for all registered nurses on a global scale. Now, in the twenty-first century, official organizations, schools, and continuing education which help prepare nurses for engaging in informatics related practice are springing up all over the world especially in technologically advanced nations. There is however a growing need for practicing registered nurses, nurse educators, nurse researchers, nurse administrators and managers to ensure that the expected competencies in informatics are met. Nurses certified in nursing informatics are skilled in the analysis, design, and implementation of information systems that support nursing in a

variety of healthcare setting, functions as translators between nurse clinical and information technology personnel and ensure that information systems capture clinical nursing information.

Social media and ethics

The Advent of Social Media networks like WhatsApp, Facebook, twitter, Instagram, LinkedIn etc, has created essential communication tools for all professionals. In conjunction with mobile technologies, they have rapidly changed and will continue to evolve as everyday tool for effective interactions. These developments have created a new dilemma as ethics in social media has resulted in new ethical issues not covered by nursing ethics.

Cultural differences can make it difficult to determine what is unethical, especially when it comes to using computers. Studies on ethics and computer use reveal that people of different nationalities have different views, difficulties arise when the ethical conduct of a regional group.

Evidence based practice in nursing informatics in Nigeria

In Nigeria, information infrastructure is essential for evidence-based practice. There are five basic infrastructure blocks for evidence-based practice: 1) common terminology and structures, 2) sources of digital evidence, 3) standards that facilitate the exchange of health care data among heterogeneous systems, 4) information processes that support the acquisition application of evidence on a specific clinical situation, and 5) information competencies.

When put in place, each of these blocks supports the application of evidence to practice and builds evidence from practice. Suzanne,(2001).

Nursing Ethics and Informatics Education

Over the last 10 years, developing nursing informatics has been a vital subject in both nursing education and practices. However, informatics introduction is still far from the syllabus of many nursing schools. As a result, undergraduate students are not aware with many of the past and current ethical dilemmas arising from scientific growth. In relation to nursing ethics and informatics grounding provides an excellent environment for introducing young scientists and future health care professionals to ethical problems that will undoubtedly face high schools and their professional careers. It is thus very important that all nursing schools provide adequate teaching of informatics to their students to expose these nursing professionals to the ethical problems they will undoubtedly face.

Nursing education should prepare nurses to function independently and/or as members of interdisciplinary and intersectoral health care team. Strategies must be put in place to providing nursing informatics education within nursing training programmes. There is thus the need to imbibe among nurses a culture that promotes and acceptance the use of information technology as an important initiative towards establishing nursing informatics

competencies and educational strategies to achieve nursing informatics competencies in the workplace include in-service training, internet ready modules for teaching and learning purposes, free access to online resources, and opportunities for continuing education.

Using informatics, Nursing Education will overcome the dilemma involved in computerized record keeping, computerized assisted instruction, interactive video technology (Telenursing), distance learning web based courses and degree programmes, and teaching and presentations.

FUNDAMENTAL ETHICAL PRINCIPLES

Some of the fundamental ethical principles resulting from the interplay of nursing care and informatics include:

Beneficence and Non-maleficence; to seek benefit from those who work with them and are careful not to harm. In their professional work, psychologists seek to preserve the well-being and rights of those who interact professionally with them and other affected persons, and the well-being of animal research topics.

Fidelity and Responsibility; to develop trusting relationships with those who work with them. They are aware of their professional and scientific responsibilities towards the community and the specific communities in which they work.

Integrity; to seek to promote accuracy, honesty and honesty in science, teaching and practicing well.

Justice; recognition of justice and justice qualify all people to access and benefit from the contributions and equal quality in the processes, procedures and services Heiskell, (2010).

Respect for People's Rights and Dignity; to respect the dignity and worth of all people, the rights of individuals to privacy, confidentiality and self-determination Heiskell, (2010).

Autonomy; Agree to respect the right of the other to self-determination; and to support independent decision-making Heiskell, (2010).

Paternalism; Health care professionals make decisions about treating, and diagnosing the patient. Based on the belief of the health care professional about what is in the patient's best interest, he chooses to reveal or obscure the patient information in these three important areas.

This principle is heavily loaded as an application of authority to the patient Heiskell, (2010).

ETHICAL DECISION MAKING

Attention to our feelings can be important evidence that we are facing an ethical dilemma.

Ethical emotions are part of our makeup as humans. These feelings are triggered even when we do not have a personal interest in the event [23]. Attempts of moral education to prepare individuals to recognize and respond effectively to ethical dilemmas. The study of different philosophical styles of ethics, evaluation of decisions and outcomes of past and ethical problems, and

discussion of effective case studies are some ways in which individuals can acquire the skills necessary to make ethical decisions [24].

INFORMATICS AND NURSING RESEARCH ETHICS

Nurses spend a significant proportion of their time on information related activities as part of clinical decision making in order to lead, co-ordinate and support the delivery of safe, effective, person centered care. In order to provide high quality care for patients, Olubiyi, (2008) pointed out that nurses need up-to-date, accurate, relevant information about the person and access to the latest evidence or best practice at the point of care delivery. Since research in nursing is necessary for the development of nursing practice, it is important that a proper understanding of informatics is essential as it will help drive research efforts on current trends and developments in nursing practice in Nigeria. This will help resolve some dilemma on computerized literature searching, retrieval of evidence based nursing practice, adoption of standardized language related to nursing terminologies, the ability to find data derived from large population groups statistical software, adoption of epidemiology -information analysis and the use of knowledge based internet.

The dilemma encounter in nursing research can be overcome using the following guiding which are clear, unmistakable and easily applied ethical codes of informatics;

- Research participants must voluntarily consent to research participation.
- The research aims should

- contribute to the good of society.
- Research must be based on sound theory and prior animal testing.
- Research must avoid unnecessary physical and mental suffering.
- No research projects can go forward where serious injury and/or death are potential outcomes.
- The degree of risk taken by research participants cannot exceed anticipated benefits of results.
- Proper environment and protection for participants is necessary.
- Experiments can be conducted only by scientifically qualified persons.
- Human subjects must be allowed to discontinue their participation at any time.
- Scientists must be prepared to terminate the experiment if there is cause to believe that continuation will be harmful or result in injury or death.

Moreover, since the field of informatics is in a state of constant change, it should be flexible in order to accommodate changes that are taking place without sacrificing the application of fundamental nursing principles.

Barriers to Nursing Informatics Competency

There are various barriers that are perceived to have contributed to the poor competency in utilization of nursing informatics in practice. Some of them include;

- Inadequate number of computers
- Limited access to computer
- Long log in time
- Discouragement
- Unreliable network
- Work load
- Too old to learn
- Low IT knowledge
- Lack of confidence
- Shortage of staff
- Lack of interest
- Wrong notion about computers

CONCLUSION

Nursing ethical dilemma is whether virtue is something that can be taught or whether it is something within our human nature that cannot be changed and an individual is pre-disposed to it. This review explored; nursing ethical dilemma in using informatics technology, nurses ethics, informatics ethics, social media and ethics, evidence based practice in nursing informatics, bioethics, fundamental ethical principles, ethical decision making, research ethics, the code of ethics, and challenges facing the adoption of informatics in nursing practice in Nigeria.. Nursing informatics is a new nursing specialty in Nigeria; even though it was approved by the American Nurses Association in 1992 as a recognized specialty and has since been growing. The building blocks of this specialty are nursing, information and

computer sciences. These three combined provide the knowledge base of nursing informatics. Expanded roles and technology are being incorporated into the domain of nursing informatics. The effects of these roles are visible across all sectors of nursing. This paper explores the field of nursing informatics and presents the relevance to contemporary nursing.

Therefore, to function in the increasingly complex healthcare environment, every nurse is required to have basic computer competencies, be able to access, use and evaluate relevant nursing information and possess information management skills. Nurse Faculty, Nurse/Midwife educators who are vested with the responsibility of producing the crop of nurses who have the capabilities to fit into the current trend of nursing practice. Literature has shown that comprehensive informatics content is lacking in the nursing curricular at all levels of nursing education in Nigeria. There is preponderance of evidence showing that training in *Nursing informatics* is critical in the delivery of safe and quality patient care. Thus Nursing programme accrediting bodies in Nigeria (National University Commission [NUC] and Nursing and Midwifery Council of Nigeria [NMCN]) should modify their requirements to reflect the value of Nursing Informatics and ensure it is fully incorporated into the nursing curricular at all levels to reduce the dilemma nurses face using

informatics technology in practices in Nigeria.

Furthermore, informatics. Faculty members & Nurse/Midwife educators should acquire informatics training and advocate for curricular changes that incorporate informatics and collaborate with colleagues in the clinical settings to provide opportunities for nursing students to utilize informatics tools.

Nursing leaders in all areas including research, education and administration and the Nursing and Midwifery Council of Nigeria have a big role to play in ensuring that nursing informatics is embraced by all nurses in Nigeria.

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